

Binary and Ternary Complexes of Interest to Environmental Systems. Part—II : Interaction of Beryllium(II) with a Mixture of Ligands and Failure in Forming Mixed Ligand Complexes

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Potentiometric studies on systems of the type ML/L' [$M=Be(II)$, $L'=8$ -hydroxyquinoline-5-sulfonic acid (HQS), $L''=benzohydroxamic$ acid (BHA) or salicylic acid (SA) or one of the derivatives of SA] revealed that mixed ligand complexes are not formed although binary complexes of high stability are formed.

RECENTLY the importance of mixed ligand complexes in environmental chemistry¹, medicinal chemistry², analytical chemistry³ and industrial chemistry⁴ has led to a large number of reports on the formation and stabilities of mixed ligand complexes⁵. Literature shows that there is little work relating to non-transition elements and none whatsoever on Be(II). The high toxicity of beryllium and the sources through which it can enter the environment⁶ made it necessary to study its mixed ligand complexes. Though the results indicated an absence of mixed ligand complex formation in the Be(II)-benzohydroxamic acid and Be-salicylate systems, the study provided very useful information.

Experimental

All chemicals were reagent grade unless specified. Methyl salicylic acids (K and K Laboratories, New York) were treated with charcoal in ethanol and crystallised. Salicylic acid was crystallised from double distilled water. The purity of all the acids was checked by comparing their m.p. with literature values⁷.

3-Methyl-5-sulfosalicylic acid (3-M-5-SSA) was prepared by sulfonating 3-methyl salicylic acid (3-MSA) by heating it (20 g) with 30 ml fuming sulphuric acid (20% oleum). The mixture was continuously stirred, cooled to maintain the temperature, and kept for 24 hr. It was filtered in a sintered funnel, the paste dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and the solution was allowed to crystallise. The crystals were washed several times with minimum quantity of water followed by minimum quantity of ether, so as to free them from sulphate ions, and dried first in air and then in a desiccator. The elemental analysis (Found : C, 35.97 ; O, 47.91 ; S, 12.03. Calcd. : C, 36.36 ; O, 47.76 ; S, 11.94%) and molecular weight, 268, showed the composition

as $C_9H_{12}O_6S$ which corresponds to the formula $HO_3S.C_6H_4.CH_3.OH.COOH.2H_2O$.

4-Methyl-5-sulfosalicylic acid (4-M-5-SSA) was prepared by sulfonating 4-methyl salicylic acid (4-MSA) as described above. It was purified by repeated recrystallisation, first with water and then with water-ethanol mixture. The sample prepared was colourless, m.p. $90 \pm 1^\circ$, agrees well with literature⁷ value.

In the case of 4-M-5-SSA, there is a possibility of formation of the 3-sulfo derivative (m.p. 101°) in addition to the 5-sulfo derivative. That only one isomer was present was confirmed by tlc using ethyl alcohol-methyl ethyl ketone-formic acid-water (50 : 30 : 10 : 10) solvent. The R_f found was 0.72.

The analytical data (Found : C, 31.19 ; O, 52.38 ; S, 10.93. Calcd. : C, 31.58 ; O, 52.63 ; S, 10.52%) and molecular weight of the acid by titrating it against standard alkali, which comes to 304, gave its formula as $HO_3S.C_6H_4.CH_3.OH.COOH.4H_2O$.

The 3-sulfo-5-methyl-salicylic acid (3-S-5-MSA) was prepared by sulfonating 5-methyl salicylic acid (5-MSA) as described earlier. The product was recrystallised several times, first with water and then with alcohol-water mixture, and was dried before its melting point was checked⁷.

The ligands, especially the unsulfonated ones, were difficult to dissolve in water. Their concentrated aqueous solutions were prepared by converting them to their monosodium salts using sodium hydroxide. Prior to titration they were reverted to the free-ligand forms by the addition of equivalent amounts of perchloric acid.

Potentiometric studies :

For the study of binary systems titrations were performed at 35° and in an atmosphere of N_2 (O_2

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES OF BERYLLIUM(II) WITH SALICYLIC ACID (SA), ITS DERIVATIVES AND BENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID

$\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄), Temp. 35°

Ligand	log K _{H1}	log K _{H2}	log K _{BeS} ^{Be*}	log K _{BeS₂} ^{BeS**}	log B _{BeS₂} ^{Be*}
3-Sulfo-5-methyl-SA	13.47	2.52	12.75	9.00	21.75
SA	13.24	2.32	12.69	9.65	22.34
3-Methyl-5-sulfo-SA	12.58	2.54	12.04	8.99	21.03
4-Methyl-5-sulfo-SA	12.33	2.68	12.72	9.25	21.97
5-Sulfo-SA	11.90	2.44	11.61	8.95	20.56
Benzohydroxamic acid	8.68	—	8.70	7.27	15.97

$$\log K_{BeS}^{Be} = \log \frac{[BeS]}{[Be][S]}$$

$$** \log K_{BeS_2}^{BeS} = \log \frac{[BeS_2]}{[BeS][S]}$$

$$* \log K_{BeS_2}^{Be} = \log \frac{[BeS_2]}{[Be][S]^2}$$

S=SA or one of its derivatives and BHA, Be=Be(II); aquo molecules have been omitted for the sake of brevity.

and CO₂ free) with carbonate free 0.1000 M NaOH on 50 ml solutions containing 0.1 M. NaClO₄ and the following :

(i) 0.10 M HClO₄, (ii) 0.010 M HClO₄ + 1.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand, (iii) 0.010 M HClO₄ + 1.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand + 1.0 × 10⁻³ metal ion, (iv) 0.10 M HClO₄ + 1.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand + 2.0 × 10⁻³ M metal ion. Titration (iv) in each sequence enabled one to study both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal-ligand complexes. The calculation of free ligand concentration, \bar{n} , and log K were done as described⁸ elsewhere using a computer program CECADS. The method is, in essence, a combination of Irving and Rossotti's⁹ and Block and McIntyre's¹⁰ methods but takes into account all possible equilibria.

The mixed ligand titrations were performed with 0.1000 M NaOH solution on 50 ml solutions containing 0.1 M NaClO₄ + 0.010 M HClO₄ + 1.0 × 10⁻³ M metal ion + 1.0 × 10⁻³ M HQS or 1.0 × 10⁻³ M BHA or SA or one of the derivatives of SA under conditions similar to those in which 1 : 1 metal-ligand titrations were done.

Results and Discussion

Ternary system :

The stability constants of the complexes of Be(II) with HQS and its derivatives are of the order of 5-7 log units¹¹ which is several units less than stabilities of Be(II)-salicylates (Table 1). It was thought that in mixtures containing Be(II), HQS and salicylic acids, Be(II) would form stable complexes with salicylic acids at lower pH which would add up HQS molecules to form mixed ligand complexes.

The results of potentiometric studies, however, indicate that the 1 : 1 Be(II)-salicylic acid system formed (at pH 2-4) prefers hydroxo ions to HQS anions at higher pH values. In the ternary Be(II)-HQS-MSA system (Table 2) precipitation is observed at a ≈ 3 (where a represents the number of moles of base added per mole of ligand), the pH of precipitation being the same as for the binary system. The results, however, indicate that a turbidity appears at a ≈ 3 in the ternary system. The 'composite'¹² curve (figure not shown) is superimposable

TABLE 2—DATA FROM THE POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF MIXTURES CONTAINING BERYLLIUM(II) AND SALICYLIC ACID WITH AND WITHOUT 8-HYDROXYQUINOLINE-5-SULFONIC ACID

[Be(II)] = 0.0010 M, SA = 0.0010 M, HQS = 0.0010 M
 $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄), Temp. = 35°, [NaOH] = 0.1000 M.

Titration of mixture containing Be(II) and SA with NaClO₄ Titration of mixture containing Be(II), HQS and SA with NaClO₄

a	pH	a*	pH
0.0	3.02	1.0	3.05
0.4	3.30	1.4	3.30
0.5	3.42	1.6	3.45
0.8	3.60	1.8	3.60
1.0	3.75	2.0	3.77
1.2	3.93	2.2	4.00
1.4	4.32	2.4	4.35
1.6	4.71	2.6	4.65
1.8	5.40	2.8	5.95
2.0	6.20	3.0	6.10
2.2	7.10 [†]	3.2	7.02 [†]

* It is presumed that in the region 0 < a ≤ 1 the -SO₃H group of HQS is neutralised.

† Appearance of a turbidity.

on the ternary system titration curve. There is, therefore, no indication of a metal-mixed ligand complex formation in solution.

The 1 : 1 complex of Be(II) with benzohydroxamic acid (BHA) is unipositive unlike the 1 : 1 Be(II)-SA complex which is neutral. Potentiometric studies (Table 3), here too, fail to indicate mixed ligand complex formation inspite of availability of unipositively charged Be-BHA complex.

Binary system :

The formation constants of binary complexes are recorded in Table 1.

In all titrations with Be(II) and salicylic acid or its derivatives, buffer regions were observed at 0 < a < 2 and 2 < a < 4, with inflexions at a ≈ 2 and a ≈ 4 indicating the stepwise formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. In non-sulfonated ligands, precipitation occurred at a ≈ 4. The \bar{n} value steadily increased with pH to ≈ 2 indicating the formation of 1 : 2 complex as the highest complex in Be(II)-

TABLE 3—DATA FROM THE POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF MIXTURES CONTAINING BERYLLIUM(II) AND BENZO-HYDROXAMIC ACID WITH AND WITHOUT 8-HYDROXY-QUINOLINE-5-SULFONIC ACID

[Be(II)]=0.0010 M, [BHA]=0.0010 M, [HQS]=0.0010 M
 $\mu=0.1$ M (NaClO₄), Temp.=35°, [NaOH]=0.1000 M

Titration of mixture containing Be(II) and BHA with NaClO ₄		Titration of mixture containing Be(II), BHA and HQS with NaClO ₄	
a	pH	a*	pH
0.0	4.50	1.0	4.51
0.4	4.72	1.4	4.70
0.6	4.87	1.6	4.85
0.8	4.95	1.8	4.90
1.0	5.10	2.0	5.07
1.2	5.35	2.2	5.25
1.4	5.60	2.4	5.50
1.6	6.00	2.6	5.87
1.8	6.20	2.8	6.10
2.0	6.35*	3.0	6.55*

* In the region $0 < a \leq 1$, the free hydrochloric acid present with the BHA solution is neutralised.

* Appearance of turbidity.

salicylic acid system. Absence of disproportionation and constancy of \bar{n} in the pH range 7-10 in Be(II) complexes of sulfonated salicylic acids point towards their resistance to hydrolysis. In Be(II)-BHA system buffer regions were observed at $0 < a < 1$ and $1 < a < 2$, and inflexions at $a \approx 1$ and $a \approx 2$. The maximum value of \bar{n} was 2, which implies that highest complex in this system is 1 : 2 :: metal : ligand.

In the calculation of metal-ligand equilibrium constants, the values of salicylic acid basicities determined spectrophotometrically by the method of Chattopadhyaya^{1,8} at 35° and in 0.1 M NaClO₄ medium have been used because potentiometric methods cannot be relied upon to obtain accurate results for the highly basic phenolic dissociation constants of salicylic acids.

In all systems, except Be(II)-4-M-5-SSA, the stability of 1 : 1 complexes followed the order of the log K_{H₁} (phenolic group protonation constant) values of salicylic acids¹. The unusually high stability of Be(II)-4M-5-SSA system could not be explained although it was found to be reproducible. The stabilities of 1 : 2 complexes of 3-S-5-MSA and 3-M-5-SSA also defy the order of the basicity of corresponding salicylic acids. This is possibly due to the steric hindrance of substituent groups which are ortho to the coordination sites in these acids.

The steric hindrance is not very pronounced in the log K_{BeS}^{Be} values because the 1 : 1 complex involves a reaction between the dipositive Be(II) ion and the trinegative ligand anion. Such reactions are facilitated by the coulombic attraction between the ions in question but in the formation of 1 : 2 complex, which involves a mononegative 1 : 1 complex and the trinegative ligand anion, the coulombic attraction is replaced by repulsion and the steric factors become operative.

The higher stability of complexes of sulfo-methyl-salicylic acids give the corresponding ligands an edge over 5-sulfosalicylic acid as complexing agents for Be(II). It has been shown^{1,8} that if salicylic acid is regarded as a reference substance, then in the case of metal complexes of substituted salicylic acids, the wavelength of maximum absorption (λ_{max}) and molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) at λ_{max} increases in presence of -SO₃H and -CH₃ groups. This possibility together with lower water solubility and stronger beryllium affinity of 3-MSA and 4-MSA in comparison to SA makes the methyl-salicylic acids potentially better extracting agents for Be(II) than SA. The superiority of sulfo-methyl salicylic acids over SSA as colorimetric reagents has already been demonstrated in their use for microdetermination of cerium and cobalt^{1,4}.

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